

The Techno -Economic and Environmental Assessments of Grid-connected Photovoltaic Systems in Bhubaneswar, India

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Abstract : The power system utility has started to think about the green power technology in order to have an eco-friendly environment. The green power technology utilizes renewable energy sources for reduction of GHG emissions. Odisha state (India) is very rich in potential of renewable energy sources especially in solar energy (about 300 solar days), for installation of grid connected photovoltaic system. This paper focuses on the utilization of photovoltaic systems in an Institute building of Bhubaneswar city, Odisha. Different data like solar insolation (kW/m²/day), sunshine duration has been collected from metrological stations for Bhubaneswar city. The required electrical power and cost are calculated for daily load of 1.0 kW. The HOMER (Hybrid Optimization Model of Electric Renewable) software is used to estimate system size and its performance analysis. The simulation result shows that the cost of energy (COE) is \$ 0.194/kWh, the Operating cost is \$63/yr and the net present cost (NPC) is \$3,917. The energy produced from PV array is 1,756kWh/yr and energy purchased from grid is 410 kWh/yr(19% fraction). The AC primary load consumption is 1314 kWh/yr and the Grid sales are 746 kWh/yr. One battery is connected in parallel with 12V DC Bus and the usable nominal capacity 2.4 kWh with 9.6 h autonomy capacity.

Keywords : Economic assessment, HOMER, Optimization, Photovoltaic (PV), Renewable energy

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